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**Solo self-employment, worker entrepreneurship, crowdworking
and co. Flexible working and its consequences.**

**Abridged version of the TA-SWISS study: «Flexible neue Arbeitswelt.
Eine Bestandsaufnahme auf gesellschaftlicher und volkswirtschaftlicher Ebene»**

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Flexible neue Arbeitswelt. Eine Bestandsaufnahme auf gesellschaftlicher und volkswirtschaftlicher Ebene

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Flexible working in brief	4
Its opportunities	4
... its risks	5
... and some recommendations	5
Increasing diversity in the world of work	6
Locationally and temporally flexible.....	6
Flatter hierarchies, vanished boundaries.....	6
Working in the «Human Cloud».....	7
Broader range of professional biographies.....	7
Individual characteristics with consequences for society	8
Increased productivity with no guarantee of more pay	9
Proper balance between career and private life.....	9
Not without risk for psychological and physical health	11
Social security on shaky ground.....	11
When the payment flow disappears underground	11
Atypical employment in the legal grey area	12
Special laws in response to flexibilisation.....	13
Personal equipment in company use	13
Clarification of details required	13
Good training as trump card in the flexible world of work	15
Heightening awareness of the subjectification of work.....	15
Flexible working as common task.....	16
Remove legal shortcomings	16
Know more in order to be able to act at the right time.....	16

Flexible working in brief

A job for one's entire working life, with regulated office working hours from eight in the morning until six in the evening – this model belongs in the past. Many people now work on the train and on the bus, from home or at the client's premises. And they also work on a job late in the evening or even in the small hours of the morning when everyone else is asleep. Work has become flexible: in terms of location and time, but also of content. Businesses too are increasingly elastic in their forward planning. For instance, they allow longer periods of time off and part-time working, and set up project-based working groups for which they also sometimes hire external specialist workers on a temporary basis. Even wages are no longer a fixed value, but can be linked to business performance.

In this environment, Swiss employment law compares favourably with that in other European countries. It allows sufficient organisational scope and safeguards employees materially and with regard to their rights and health protection. But the question is, whether the existing legal and institutional framework can still respond to foreseeable changes in the world of work.

Its opportunities ...

Employees can more easily implement their personal life plan if their company doesn't impose any daily attendance hours at the firm's own workplace and they are now even allowed to take more time off. The home office makes it easier for many people to better reconcile their career with family and other commitments, and project work in interchangeable teams is preferred by many people, especially those who are younger and well qualified. And if anyone wishes to earn a little extra on top of their main professional activity, or even become fully self-employed, they can access global demand and jobs via so-called crowdsourcing platforms on the internet.

... its risks ...

If the workplace is no longer tied to a fixed location and the line between leisure time and professional activity are opened up, high demands are placed on the discipline of employees and their ability to set their own boundaries. When professional activity begins to monopolise their leisure time, long-term fatigue, or even burnout threaten. And an improvised workplace that forces them to adopt a poor posture can damage their health. The social security benefits provided by the existing employment law is undermined by new forms of cooperation: for example, someone who regularly carries out jobs for web-based employment agencies is regarded as self-employed and is not entitled to paid leave, or to support if they fall ill or are unemployed. Provision for old age is at risk, and without a regulated contract of employment there is even a question mark over their subsistence needs. From a macroeconomic point of view, the problem is that income and turnover tax cannot be easily applied if the paid work is increasingly shifted into the legal grey areas of the internet.

... and some recommendations

- Society must generally be sensitised to the subjectification of work that can open up greater freedom of movement for employees but also demands more responsibility.
- Operational flexibility places considerable demands on both supervisors and employees and must be planned as participative organisational development.
- From a legal viewpoint, the shortcomings in respect of social insurance must be corrected for short-time work deployments, and clarification given for the questions of how the regulations applicable in this

country can be enforced in the case of international working relationships and how the status of false self-employment must be recorded.

- Finally, the official statistics would have to take into account the new phenomena such as crowdworking with a view to the future, not least so that the threat of a hidden economy can be countered in good time.

The present summary is based on the study «Flexible neue Arbeitswelt» (Flexible new world of work) that has been produced under the leadership of Jens O. Meissner and Johann Weichbrodt by a project team from the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts and the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland.

Increasing diversity in the world of work

Digitalisation has become largely established at the workplace. In the process it is helping to make professional activity increasingly flexible and enabling it to be adapted for the individual and to the needs of employers. Working life is pulsating – everywhere and around the clock.

In the fourth quarter of 2015 the Swiss Federal Statistical Office recorded five million workers in Switzerland; that is almost 70 percent of the permanently resident population. Approximately 650,000 persons, i.e. around 13 percent, are self-employed – a figure that has barely changed in the past 20 years. At the same time, a further 230,000 plus people were looking for a job, with the unemployment rate at the end of 2015 amounting to 4.7 percent.

Locationally and temporally flexible

For many people, professional activity – or the desire for it – is part of their everyday lives. But working conditions that remain the same over an extended period of time have long been something that cannot be taken for granted anymore, and even working hours have become flexible. In this country, over 30 percent of the working population work part time, a figure that, on the European level, is only exceeded in the Netherlands. About 5 percent do on-call work, and around 7 percent of all employment contracts are fixed-term. About 61 percent of Swiss workers use flexible working hours in the form of flexitime or other adjustable models, and around 17 percent do not record their actual working hours.

In addition to temporal flexibilisation, which has already been introduced several decades ago, locational flexibility is more recent. About a quarter of employees work from home at least on certain weekdays, in the so-called home office. Linked via the internet, many people can even access their company's data directly. Even on

the move it is possible to perform professional activities – in «third locations», such as on the train, or in a street café, or on site at the customer's premises. In this case, a smartphone or tablet are enough to carry out a great many tasks.

Businesses are also increasingly no longer providing their employees with a personal workplace. Large employers in particular, such as the Swiss Federal Railways (SBB) and Swiss Post, practice so-called

desk-sharing at their main offices and hence rely on locational flexibility within the company premises: employees then choose the site best suited for the particular activity and task at hand.

Flatter hierarchies, vanished boundaries

In addition to these relatively clearly recognisable forms of work flexibilisation, there are also shifts in competencies and entrepreneurial responsibility that

are more difficult to grasp. Rather than employees having to restrict themselves to following the instructions of their superiors, they are allowed greater freedom of action so that they achieve preset targets on their own. This transfer of entrepreneurial risk and the corresponding responsibility to employees can therefore go hand in hand with variable wage components being linked to corporate success. Sociologists have coined the term «entremployee» or «employee entrepreneur». That underlines the fact that flexibilisation of work tends to lead to a blurring of the previously clear boundaries between the status of employees and self-employed workers. The once clear dividing line between working and leisure time is also becoming fuzzy.

Finally, thanks to digitalisation, activities that were previously performed within an enterprise are being outsourced to specialised external service companies. This «outsourcing» is nothing new in itself. However, inter-company collaboration is being increasingly stretched to encompass the entire globe: India for instance was long regarded as a Mecca for IT services, before the increasing complexity of many applications led a number of firms from Europe to bring their commissions back to countries that are closer geographically and culturally.

Working in the «Human Cloud»

Even more recent, finally, are electronic platforms that bring jobseekers and clients together – they act as a sort of digital job portal. Platforms such as Amazon's «Mechanical Turk» or the German agency «Clickworker» focus on the large number of workers who can be recruited internationally, and are able to divide larger jobs into sometimes the smallest micro-jobs. There are as yet few reliable data on the relatively

new phenomenon of crowdsourcing or crowdworking, but this type of placing or procuring contracts could in future grow in importance. Particularly in the internet-orientated technology sectors there are personnel supervisors who assume that over the next few years their company will lay off up to two-thirds of its fixed workforce and recruit the additional manpower it needs from the huge reservoir of specialists («Human Cloud») available via the internet as «Liquid Talents». Satisfied users of such platforms praise the possibility of being able to earn some pocket money quickly and with no complications. Critics, however, complain about on-call online work that encourages the creation of a new precariat. Another negative factor from this point of view are the intransparent payments that can evade the tax authorities and thus encourage the web-based hidden economy.

Broader range of professional biographies

The flexibilisation of work opens up countless possibilities for reconciling professional activity with individual preferences and life plans. But freer choice also involves risks: offsetting more self-determination against a relatively low salary may be attractive when one is young, but there may be no material security in one's old age. The study by TA-SWISS attempts to capture the new range of professional biographies by creating five different types of workers – so-called «personas» – and showing the potential consequences of their everyday professional life in the most positive and the most unprofitable cases (see box).

Flexible world of work, reflected in five «personas»

A steady full time management position as finance manager of an SME, with the possibility of working one day a week in a home office: Persona «Roland Müller» largely corresponds by today's standards to the conventional. Persona «Sandra Könitz», unmarried, living in a relationship and mother of two, works full time for a consulting firm as a highly qualified specialist in economics and law. In addition to her consultancy work, she also attracts new mandates. She works from home but also on site at the client's premises and wherever she happens to be. If the company makes a profit at the end of the year she receives a bonus. «Ursula Meyerhans», living in a partnership but with no children, is employed by a magazine as a part-time editor. In addition to that she writes advertising brochures for upmarket technical products as a freelance copywriter and contributes journalistic articles on various crowdsourcing platforms covering the most varied topics. «Noah Schmid», in a firm relationship with no children, earns his money as a self-employed software developer by programming webshops for small companies. To supplement his income he accepts website design jobs from different crowdsourcing platforms. He is also working to develop an app to facilitate the payment of relatively small sums of money with a smartphone – and from which he expects fairly high earnings should it one day be successful. Persona «Andrea Burri-Lötscher», finally, married and mother of two children, abandoned her studies as a chef. Today she works as a part time kitchen assistant in a nursing home, and takes on assistance services jobs in private homes or as an office cleaner via an internet employment agency. She also looks after her elderly in-laws.

Individual characteristics with consequences for society

Flexible working has consequences for most people who are in employment, both advantageous and disadvantageous. Taken overall, the foreseeable changes in the world of work will have repercussions for society as a whole. The social consequences of flexible and individualised working can be measured using a variety of indicators.

The flexibilisation of the world of work impacts on hitherto firmly established professional roles: in addition to today's normal working relationship defined by an open-ended employment contract for full-time employment with a clearly set out performance specification, an increasing number of entrepreneurs as defined above are emerging onto the scene. It is also to be expected that working people will more often combine one or more part-time positions with jobs that they carry out on a fee basis. The proportion of self-employed could also increase. For by reducing their fixed workforce to a minimum and by taking on external support at times of high workload («numerical flexibility»), many businesses are creating conditions which persuade more working people to become self-employed: some of them because they anticipate a healthy order book since many of the big firms increasingly rely on outsourcing certain tasks, others – especially low qualified workers – lose their jobs and switch to self-employment out of necessity.

The five «personas» defined above embody different characteristics of the professional biographies that are starting to appear. The consequences that society as a whole would have to expect if in future one or two of the five ideal types were to become widespread have been extrapolated from the TA-SWISS study using statistics and specialist literature.

Increased productivity with no guarantee of more pay

Productivity is a measure that correlates expenditure and income. At the macroeconomic level, labour and capital are generally regarded as expenditure and the earnings achieved as income. From the point of view of individual working people, productivity is measured by the number of hours they need to complete their work and how much they earn in the process.

A permanent job with one or two working days in the home office – embodied by the persona «Roland Müller» – might in the short term raise productivity: no journey to the office and the time saved, together with the domestic working environment, boost motivation. However, studies indicate that productivity declines after two or three days in the home office. The demarcation between private life and professional activity in particular proves problematic for many people.

Mobile work that is practised within a contractually permanent job – exemplified by the consultancy specialist Sandra Könitz – could bring a productivity growth, at both individual and macroeconomic levels. That is because the emphasis here is very much on autonomy, and if the results defined by the employing firm can be best achieved autonomously and interpreted as milestones for one's own success, that encourages maximum performance. At operational level too, mobile working raises productivity, because it offers the company a potential saving of up to 20 percent on operating costs by not having to provide a fixed workplace for all of its employees. Moreover, thanks to flexible working hours they can better adjust the deployment of their staff to the workload and thus plan ahead with the aim of improving productivity.

If working people supplement different part-time positions with jobs obtained independently, it is only the employing businesses which profit from higher productivity, because this model, represented by the persona «Ursula Meyerhans», is particularly ideal for increasing productivity in firms with widely fluctuating order books. However, there has been scarce scientific research until now on how temporary employment contracts impact on individual productivity. Empirical data points rather to a negative effect, because compared with workers employed on an open-ended basis temporary employees tend to work unpaid overtime, while unilaterally having to assume the financial burden of the idle times. In the working world of Ursula Meyerhans different effects could therefore be reciprocally offset, so that work productivity will barely change compared to now.

The persona «Noah Schmid» represents the solo self-employed group: that's what the experts call working people who are self-employed alone, i.e. with no employees. International studies show that productivity in countries with a high quota of self-employed tends to fall, because small companies can rarely organise their work as efficiently as large firms. However, there is a considerable distinction between people who have become self-employed involuntarily in order to avoid unemployment and those who see an opportunity in self-employment to realise their own potential creatively and correspondingly show high enthusiasm and ambition in their professional commitment. Professional qualification is therefore a significant key to high productivity. This is most obviously apparent with the persona «Andrea Burri-Lötscher», who has no professional qualification: aggregate productivity in her working world at best increases slightly but actually tends to fall. That is because even if overall more working hours are completed, low rates of pay are applied.

Earnings are directly related to productivity. Only highly qualified people therefore have any prospect of higher income from flexible working. In any case, only consultancy expert Sandra Könitz can count on more pay, thanks in particular to a performance-based component – for which there is, however, no guarantee. Sporadic work in the home office of the Roland Müller type does not, however, alter the payment day. The combination of several part-time posts with jobs obtained independently (Ursula Meyerhans), as with solo self-employment (Noah Schmid), therefore result in mostly falling income. Low-qualified workers of the Andrea Burri-Lötscher model even run the risk of slipping into precarious circumstances.

Proper balance between career and private life

Combined with permanent employment and social security benefits, the great advantage of flexible working lies in the fact that it makes it easier to reconcile professional activity with other commitments – whether in the family or in leisure time. Many employees do not have to travel to the office, at least on certain days, and they can make their own decisions about their time and sometimes also on the structure of their working day. This benefits both mental and physical relaxation, boosts motivation and therefore helps to make it easier to care for children and dependants and to more actively maintain friendships. Job satisfaction is correspondingly high among those workers who of their own free will opt for flexible forms of working.

Nevertheless, it is predominantly well qualified people aware of the risks of flexible working who are able to benefit from its advantages. If there is no clear separation between professional activity and leisure time, there is a risk that employees will be completely unable to switch off and get any rest. Another risk is that

employees who work in their home environment, at the customer's premises or at an improvised workplace on the move must apply considerable discipline so as not to be distracted. Workers who do not have the specific skills in demand on the labour market are in an unfavourable negotiating position and have difficulty imposing their demands in respect of wages and social security on the firms employing them. Accordingly, working people who have to work flexibly out of necessity because they would otherwise have no job at all, are much less satisfied than the average for the working population.

Not without risk for psychological and physical health

Anyone who acts relatively independently on the labour market following the model of Ursula Meyerhans, Noah Schmid or Andrea Burri-Lötscher and therefore bears more responsibility, may possibly be shouldering a burden that will become too heavy in the long term. Neither income nor job are secure, and to meet the challenge of competition and deliver the desired results, entrepreneurs rapidly tend towards self-exploitation in the form of unpaid overtime. Pressure from workload and securing a livelihood can lead to psychological and physical illnesses.

Moreover, employees at a workplace that has been installed professionally by the employing business might be less at risk of physical injury. If office equipment is left to employees themselves, at an improvised desk with poor lighting there is a potential risk of muscle tension and signs of wear resulting from incorrect posture as well as impaired eyesight caused by excessive eye strain.

Social security on shaky ground

The personas «Roland Müller» and «Sandra Könitz» – both highly qualified and permanently employed – should not expect any disadvantages from their flexible working conditions for their material security if they are ill or in old age. The editor Ursula Meyerhans, who combines different, sometimes temporary part-time jobs with independently procured jobs, must, however, be concerned that her financial scope would shrink considerably in old age or if she were to fall ill. While part-time jobs can ease the transition from unemployment into working life, the change from atypical to stable employment is less often as successful as the change between permanent jobs. Furthermore, it is temporary workers or part-time employees, rather than those in permanent normal employment, who tend to lose their jobs.

In the case of the personas «Noah Schmid» and «Andrea Burri-Lötscher» professional stability and social security are even more seriously eroded. That is because their working world is open to those self-employed workers who would otherwise have become unemployed. They get a poor deal in the predictability of their contract situation as well as in respect of material and social security, especially as they are not entitled to unemployment benefits. Illness and accident lead to loss of earnings, which is not safeguarded. In old age their circumstances even threaten to become precarious – because a low income makes it impossible to save reserves and to build up adequate provision for their old age. The situation is aggravated by the fact that people who are on their own professionally are rarely able to benefit from institutionalised training. It becomes all the more difficult for them to match their knowledge and skills to the qualifications currently on demand, and they are therefore caught in a vicious circle facing additional disadvantages on the labour market.

When the payment flow disappears underground

Crypto-currencies, such as the Bitcoin, could become more important, especially for employment and contractual relationships that take place across national borders. So-called payment providers – also known as «Third Party Payment Processors» – convert crypto-currencies within the shortest possible time into a traditional currency, accept amounts for payment and pay them to the member parties. It is conceivable that especially in sectors involved in information and communications technology, crypto-currencies will in future be increasingly used for salary payments. This is very close to a cash payment, because traceability is virtually impossible, so that payment flows via crypto-currencies are difficult to track and encourage the black economy. These forms of currency are therefore frequently linked to organised cybercrime.

If the proportion of solo self-employed people increases, there is a greater risk that income will be withheld from the tax authorities and tax revenue will therefore decrease. Experts foresee that in the coming years Switzerland too will increasingly come under the influence of these two developments.

Atypical employment in the legal grey area

The objective of Swiss employment law is to safeguard the interests of the parties involved – employers on the one hand and employees on the other – in a balanced way. In a flexible working world it will in future be a matter of protecting social achievements and organising flexible working in such a way that it benefits everyone.

Employment law provisions in Switzerland emerged at the same time as paid work. From the 14th century, craft trades in particular regulated the framework conditions of apprenticeship and the requirements for achieving the master craftsman's diploma. However, until the end of the 18th century organised guilds severely restricted the freedom to pursue a trade.

The creation in stages of employment law in the modern sense began in 1877 with the Swiss federal factory act which was followed in 1881 by provisions for the service contract in the Code of Obligations (OR). This was influenced by the French Civil Code, whose liberal spirit raised contractual freedom to be a central element of the legislation and provided for just twelve articles for relationships under labour law. The effect of this legislative caution was disadvantageous to the employees – a shortcoming that was mitigated by the first revision of the OR in 1911.

A radical revision of the service contract law followed in the 1960s, and in 1966 the enactment of the labour law under public law included the issue of a provision on the minimum duration of holiday leave. Today, employment legislation covers the three comprehensive sets of standards of individual employment law (which focuses on the individual employment contract), collective employment law (which regulates the framework conditions of collective bargaining agreements, labour disputes and associations) and employment protection with rules on, for example, pension provision, accident

protection and notice of termination, together with working and rest times.

The fact that the relationship between employees and employers in Switzerland is not subject to independent approval, but that the contract of employment is regarded as a special type of contract and regulated within general contract law, is an internationally outstanding feature. The Directives of Swiss employment contract law make no distinction here between different activities, and therefore apply to all employees of a firm – from management to cleaning staff – provided that they carry on their activity in Switzerland. Swiss employment contract law also sets out not only mandatory conditions for the protection of employees but also similar conditions favouring employers. The fact that both parties therefore meet as equals without the support of, or representation by, a third party could be unique on an international comparison.

Special laws in response to flexibilisation

Under employment law, the normal employment relationship is based on the normal employment contract and the collective bargaining agreement in accordance with the OR. Normal employment contracts and/or collective bargaining agreements regulate key aspects of the relationship between employees and employers. On the one hand these are the services to be performed, on the other hand the salary, a range of care responsibilities and social security arrangements provided by the employers. Today, however, key areas of employment law are increasingly regulated by special laws, because as a result of flexibilisation greater freedom of action and responsibility are transferred to many employees. The risks associated with this, such as the blurring of work boundaries and health protection, will therefore become omnipresent challenges.

It is vitally important to distinguish the individual contract of employment from other types of contract, and especially from the commission and service contract. Which type of contract is used is determined not least by the question of whether the employees are permanent employees or self-employed workers. This in turn depends on how the person concerned is integrated into the organisation and how the employer's authority to give instructions is organised: whereas self-employed people organise their work themselves, are free to use their time as they wish and also bear the entrepreneurial risk, salaried employees follow the instructions of their superiors and are freed from any entrepreneurial responsibility. Self-employed people generally work on an agency basis, while salaried employees are subject to the individual contract of employment. The distinction between individual employment contract, specific task contract and commission is important not least in respect of notice and social security provision. Whereas in the case of the individual employment contract temporal and material protection against wrongful dismissal applies, a commission can in principle be freely revoked at any time, and social security provision lies solely with the employees.

Personal equipment in company use

The question as to if and how resources (especially: workplace equipment and devices) which the employees pay for out of their own funds should be reimbursed is legally unclear and currently under political discussion. The Code of Obligations is inconsistent in its regulation of this question: while expenses must be reimbursed (Art. 327a OR), this does not apply to the use of personal work devices that are used to carry out jobs at home or on the move. This gives rise to a legal uncertainty that the Swiss National Council has already addressed in a motion.

If more tasks are completed on the move or at home, the question of liability for loss or damage also arises. Under Art. 321e OR it is employers who are primarily liable. If, however, the computer is moved to the home and data is consequently lost, it is unclear who is responsible for this loss. In such cases, a company would do well to clarify whether the public liability insurance covers special risks (e.g. loss of data) when the work is done in a home office, or even under other mobile circumstances. Conversely, the risk for loss or damage within the company itself increases if employees use their personal mobile phones or their own computer at the company's own workplace.

This «Bring Your Own Device» (BYOD) system enhances productivity, because employees can use devices that are familiar to them. Furthermore, companies reduce their capital costs as a result. BYOD does, however, give rise to many legal questions. These relate in particular to data protection, costs and legally compliant conduct. It must, for instance, be clarified who has to pay for apps and software for a device belonging to an employee. Viewed overall, the IT policy of BYOD involves considerable risks for the employer unless it agrees a provision in the employment contract with the employees. An appropriate amendment to the contract is therefore imperative, and at the same time requires an awareness of the problem. It is essential for ownership, costs and responsibilities for data protection, licences, support and liability to be communicated.

Clarification of details required

Swiss employment law allows the social partners sufficient organisational scope to overcome the challenges inherent in the flexibilisation of labour, and at the same time to provide employees with material safeguards. Nevertheless, there are several areas of conflict.

There are at present legal uncertainties regarding the question of false self-employment. In the context of atypical employment relationships, although people often do not carry out their work within the company, and are largely free to organise their time and work, economically that nevertheless depends very much on the employing business. Such working people are not safeguarded against unemployment, nor against accidents or work-related illnesses. Moreover, there is also no occupational pension provision of any kind.

The newly emerging international working relationships, especially those procured via internet platforms are giving rise to a great many new questions. A major part of crowdsourcing takes place in a legal grey area. People who accept jobs on such crowdsourcing platforms are therefore regarded as self-employed, and the employment law provisions of the individual employment contract do not apply. Pay is based on supply and demand, and the party awarding the commission can often choose from a wide range of solutions the one that suits them best. Only the person at the top of the list in this competition for the most attractive solution will then be paid, and everyone else will have provided their service in vain. There are currently procedures ongoing in the USA that are aimed at applying the Fair Labour Standard Act to crowdsourcing, whereby crowdworkers would no longer be regarded as self-employed but as employees with the right to a minimum wage and to a certain employment protection. However, the US discussion must not be simply transferred to the situation in Switzerland, and thus many further questions are arising in this country too, such as those relating to profiteers and the obligation to submit income and turnover tax.

In coming years, in any case, it is unlikely that the momentum of technical progress will lessen, and it will

therefore be difficult for legal regulation to keep pace with the changes involved. It is all the more important to structure the legal framework in such a way that, while

not blocking any benefits of flexibilisation, protection of working people is nevertheless still assured.

Good training as trump card in the flexible world of work

At the personal, as well as the social level, the consequences of flexible working are ambiguous. Whether working people are able to make full use of its positive potential depends not so much on technology but much more on how the new forms of working are organised in practice. The study by TA-SWISS recommends a number of precautionary measures to ensure that as many people as possible can benefit from the advantages of flexible working and that its risks are localised.

The formerly sharply defined boundaries between work and leisure are becoming increasingly open. This change takes on different characteristics for all those involved. However, dealing with it successfully needs consultation, exchange and contractual regulation between all participants, on the part of both employers and employees. The legal framework for this dialogue should be broad enough to preclude extreme cases and to give the willingness to experiment sufficient scope. It is therefore essential to find arrangements that make full use of the advantages of flexible working for the benefit of the workers as well as employers and firms awarding commissions.

Heightening awareness of the subjectification of work

Simple and monotonous tasks are being increasingly left to software or robots, while employees are having to carry out more demanding jobs – increasingly on their own responsibility. On the one hand, this trend towards «worker entrepreneurship» is giving workers more freedom, in that they are planning and performing their jobs more independently, and can therefore more easily make their job compatible with other aspects of their lives. On the other hand, the requirements with regard to the training of working people are growing; this

pressure can be difficult to deal with and at the worst crush the persons concerned. It is vital to sensitise society to the phenomenon of subjectivised working. In addition, employees in this conflicting situation should be strengthened and empowered to deal competently with the opportunities and risks that are associated with the assumption of corporate responsibility. Opportunities for further training and qualification should be encouraged at every level of the company hierarchy, for example by training courses on topics such as decision making, development of negotiation and career strategies as well as time- and self-management.

Self-employed workers and people setting up their own companies do «subjectivised work» in its purest form. As part of the start-up promotion they should be advised and informed about the necessity and possibilities for social security and occupational health care schemes.

Flexible working as common task

It depends crucially on the employing firms and institutions whether flexible working in daily practice is organised for everyone's benefit. When flexible working models are introduced, this often gives rise to concerns and opposition. These must be obviated by a transparent process structure, to which all those involved can contribute on a participative basis. That is because flexible working models cannot be adopted as «ready-made solutions», but have to be adapted to the particular specific structures, cultures and requirements of a business or organisation. That often requires a joint trial phase, e.g. in the form of pilot schemes and evaluations. Operational participation and dialogue with the social partners play a crucial role when it comes to successfully implementing flexible working.

Remove legal shortcomings

Employment law does not include any regulations on modern working hours, such as annual working time, sabbaticals, long-term and the like, that are adapted for today's reality. Working models that vary from the traditional model are not infrequently inconsistent with the legal principle that codifies, for example, minimum rest times and maximum working hours within the framework of a traditional working week. The inconsistency between legal provisions that are based on a conventional working model and the realities of work today that lead to uncertainties which might have an adverse effect on the implementation of flexible working.

Flexibilisation of work could lead to an increase in short-term work assignments that are currently still concomitant with shortcomings in social insurance schemes and an unregulated security of livelihood. The growing group of workers in the «crowd», who obtain their jobs via electronic intermediation agency platforms, are also caught in a legal grey area insofar as they cannot be clearly classified either as employees or as self-employed people. In this regard the legislation on staff recruitment should also be reviewed. The Federal Act on Employment Services and the Hiring of Services should also be applied to those institutions that to a certain extent act via the internet only as an interface between self-employed «crowdworkers» and commissioning companies. In this case, international cooperation is called for, because these employment agencies, whose company headquarters are abroad, can operate outside the Swiss legal system.

Know more in order to be able to act at the right time

To register changes in the labour market promptly, reliable data are imperative. Changes of job and status and the desire to change among the working population are however only registered and published after considerable delay. Faster surveys at shorter intervals could provide a basis for reacting better to dynamic developments in the world of work.

The increasing flexibilisation of work could favour the hidden economy, and hence undermine the stability of social security provision. It is essential to identify such negative trends at the right time and to develop tools that can contribute to an effective early-warning system.

Study «Flexible neue Arbeitswelt. Eine Bestandsaufnahme auf gesellschaftlicher und volkswirtschaftlicher Ebene»

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